

THE EXPOSURE OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL FIELD TO THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF ABN SINA IN TODAY'S "ERA OF TECHNOGENIC CIVILIZATION"

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Importance of the topic: Today technique development high pictures in growth continue is doing and all in the field of this significant effect let's see possible , including pharmaceutical _ also new in the field scientific studies even " nano until the invention of the drug arrived the bride came . However each one of the thing second side as it were , man organism for each what kind of " preparation". negative effects there is . So it is pharmaceuticals field today , every ever according to more , Ibn Try it treatment to learn , and to practice application to do need we feel

Research target : Abu Ali Ibn Sino's rich scientific heritage today's of the day pharmaceuticals in the field importance and role evaluation .

Method and styles : Medicine _ science law " (" Kitab al- Kanun fi-t- tibb ") - encyclopedic in character work being , then ancient period of doctors instructions Arabic of medicine achievements with mutually again processed . In " Law". Diseases of Ibn Sina somehow small pieces due to appear to be showed . He is the first being of smallpox contagiousness attention directed , cholera and of the plague the difference identified , leprosy of the disease from others the difference showing him _ comment gave and another one series diseases by learning came out Medicine _ science of the law". Latin to the language turned many translations there is . " Law " is five from the part consists of is two _ drug tools and to medicines and their preparation to the definition dedicated . In the book 2600 drugs listed 1400 of the tools come output plant in the form of

Results : " Drug tools " ("Al- Adviyat al kalbiya ") — Hamadona the first to go on time wrote _ This is it in the work pneuma harvest when and manifestation when heart activity , in particular , the heart disease and cure about in detail light up given _ " Mistakes correction and caution through different in methods take throwing " (" Daf ' al- mazorr al kulliya an al- abdon al insaniya bi- tadorik anvo ' mistake an- event »). " Wine benefit and damage about " (" Politics al- badan and fazail ash- wine and manofi'ix and Mazorikh ») — Ibn Try it the most short pamphlet . In Arabic written encyclopedic work " Healing book " (" Kitab al- Shifa ") logic , physics , biology , psychology , geometry , arithmetic , music , astronomy and to metaphysics dedicated . " Ignorance The book "Danish-name" is also an encyclopedia is counted

Conclusions : Ibn Sina research perception from mukka gone and all there is knowledge encyclopedic level take over passion have scientist was _ Philosopher abnormal memory the owner and sharp mind the owner has been

Used books

1. Positive and Negative Aspects of the Impact of Technogenic Civilization on Human Knowledge

Citizen Abdujaliov Kozimjonovich Pulat Abdikadirov Anvarovich .

2. Junior boy bullet , ODR (2023). APPLICATION OF THE HISTORY OF MILITARY ART OF THE TIME OF AMIR TIMUR AND TIMURIS IN OUR NATIONAL ARMY TODAY. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM , 3 (34), 183-189 .
3. 3.Abdurakhmanov , Kh. I. (2020). Razvitie obshchestva i innovative thinking. In Fundamental and applied scientific research: current issues, achievements and innovations (pp . 100-102)